

Explore what *Investigating in Science* could look like to learn more about the Living World. (Table adapted from Fenton, 2011)

	Modelling	Classifying and Identifying	Pattern seeking	Making things or developing systems	Observing	Fair testing (scientific method)
This could be...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Build a model plant cell and an animal cell and investigate the significance to the organism of the differences seen <input type="checkbox"/> Create a story (words, role play, video animation, cartoons) that link familiar everyday concepts to explain how food is digested in the body. Use 'slowmation' like this example on dinosaurs <input type="checkbox"/> Make a model lung and explore how ventilation (breathing) works even though lungs are not muscles and cannot expand or contract by on their own. <input type="checkbox"/> Use a simulator and explore if it is a reasonable approximation to the real world. Try this colour vision simulator here <input type="checkbox"/> Explore how quickly a small cup of hot drink loses heat compared to a larger cup. Does a cup twice as big lose heat twice as fast? What does this mean for small animals losing heat compared to large animals? Is this experiment a good model for animals? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Collect leaves from 10 or more different named plants and see if you can sort them into groups with similar features. Create a key so that someone else could use your key to identify the plant the leaves originally came from. <input type="checkbox"/> Listen to a variety of native bird songs and investigate if certain birds are more easily identified than others. <input type="checkbox"/> Listen to a variety of native bird songs and investigate if certain calls have a particular meaning, eg, calling a mate. Alternatively, collect and group the calls of a Tui. How many different calls does a Tui have? <input type="checkbox"/> Learning from observing living animals is easier than trying to imagine the life of extinct animals. How are extinct animals identified? How can we tell what they ate? What features do extinct animals have in common? What features are different from modern living animals? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Keep a record of the times you feel tired during the day or fall asleep. Is there a pattern to when you feel the most tired? Is it linked to eating times or other behaviours? Are days on the weekend different from week days? <input type="checkbox"/> Making careful observations of your pulse rate before you drink a cup of coffee or other caffeinated drink and again afterwards. Do certain foods (eg, sugar based) or drinks affect your heart rate? <input type="checkbox"/> Ask colleagues and family to take a quick colour vision test (Ishihara plates) and see if you find any common features among those with colour vision deficiency. <input type="checkbox"/> Exploring the pattern of fingerprints from a number of different people. What are the similarities? What are the differences? Are any two the same? <input type="checkbox"/> Carry out a survey: Record where you find mussels ((the distribution) along a rocky shore and their number (the frequency). Do you see any patterns? Alternatively, look for harakeke (flax) on land. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Set up a Goldfish tank and investigate an aspect of Goldfish behaviour, eg food preference, memory length <input type="checkbox"/> Build a simple microscope from parts donated by a High School <input type="checkbox"/> Learn how to make plaster casts of animal tracks or make 'fossils' for your students to identify <input type="checkbox"/> Make a simple data logger for \$10. Use it to make an artificial eye and record UV light levels from the sun at different times of the day. Do sunglasses really block UV? <input type="checkbox"/> Make a simple interactive animation that explains how to use a piece of science equipment. <input type="checkbox"/> Research how other famous scientists made discoveries 'by luck' (serendipity) <input type="checkbox"/> Create a simple science game or simulator (Mac and PC). <input type="checkbox"/> Build a compost bin and investigate what design features make the bin work most efficiently 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Make an observational drawing of a butterfly or a fern leaf. Draw enough detail to show the main structural features and find out the name of these structures and what they do. <input type="checkbox"/> Record the stages of development of a sprouting seed placed in wet cotton wool. Record the stages from seed to the appearance of the first leaves. <input type="checkbox"/> Record the stages of decay when a piece of fruit or vegetable decomposes outside in the air. <input type="checkbox"/> Place a bird feeder in the garden. Place a variety of fruits and seeds on the feeder. Observe the species of birds that come to feed and what they feed on. Does the feeder attract anything other than birds? <input type="checkbox"/> Find a pool of water at least a week old or a cattle trough and place a drop of water into a microscope slide. Record your observations. (You could collect about 2 L of rainwater in a bucket and add a cup of soil from the garden. Leave this outside in the shade for a week) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fair testing method <input type="checkbox"/> Deciding if a project is technology or science <input type="checkbox"/> How safe are school lunches? - how hot does your lunch box get? <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate the effect of different colours of artificial light on plant growth <input type="checkbox"/> What colour flower are bees most attracted too? <input type="checkbox"/> What sounds attract birds? <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate the best conditions for edible mushroom production. <input type="checkbox"/> Does physical exercise improve learning ability? <input type="checkbox"/> Do magnetic fields around bean sprouts affect plant growth? <input type="checkbox"/> Do periods of playing computer games improve a persons reaction time? <input type="checkbox"/> How is the breakdown of a wine gum by kiwifruit juice enzymes affected by temperature?

Notes:

- The above are a few suggestions only. Please add to this document and save it for your own use on your home computer if you find it useful.
- Observations could be recorded digitally if appropriate; sounds, time lapse still images or motion video clips.
- Observational drawings are to be scientific observational drawings, with no shading. Dots and lines are allowed. The drawing must be done in pencil on A4 paper, with the specimen's name(s) printed in the lower left corner. It should be drawn directly from the observed object(s). A scale must be shown. (from [Taranaki Science Fair website](#))
- Investigations using animals must follow the guidelines outlined in this site [Caring for Animals](#) and the Animal Welfare Act 1999
- Investigations that involve practical work must follow health and safety guidelines as set out in this document ['Safety and Science Guidance Manual'](#)